

STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF GOVERNMENT ACCOUNTABILITY TO PUBLIC PERFORMANCE: THE CASE OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

KERFALI SOUHAILA, (PhD)

Management Sciences of Organizations Laboratory (LRSGO), National School of Business and Management, Ibn Tofail University -Kenitra-Morocco. Email: souhaila.kerfali@uit.ac.ma

GHARRAFI MEHDI, (PhD)

Professor-Researcher, Sidi Bennour Higher School of Technology, Chouaib Doukkali University, Morocco. Email: mehdi.gharrafi@gmail.com

Abstract

In terms of ambition, the inconclusive nature of the development of ad-hoc mission indicators, the public performance document and the public action barometer highlights the paradoxical obligation in which innovators are trapped. We're looking for an accountability tool that's light (small number of indicators), expressive (understandable by the greatest number) and properly representative of public performance. In other words, we'd like a tool that transcends the complexity and contradictions of public action - inherent in the conjunction of the State's general competence and the extreme diversity of citizens' claims, *concerns and interests*. All this is based on objectives that are, for the most part, social constructs, and therefore debatable ad nutum. The obstacle to this quest for the grail is therefore ontological.

Keywords: Public Performance- Accountability- Agricultural Sector-Public Management.

INTRODUCTION

Public performance has been at the forefront of practical and academic concerns for many years. Work on the subject has often been carried out by management control specialists on the one hand, and policy evaluators on the other. Easily associated with public value on the one hand (Moore 1995), it is connected on the other to the action theory of socio-politicians (Weiss, 1997). Comparisons between an evaluative approach to policy and a management control approach, enshrined in McDavid and Hawthorn's (2006) textbook, although increasing in number, remain relatively rare.

Linked by some to New Public Management, the quest for performance predates this movement (Bezes et alii, 2013). The multitude of interpretations to which public performance is subject, and the fact that it is put forward by a multiplicity of stakeholders, prompt us to classify it as a frontier object (Star and Griesemer 1989), at least for its interpretative ambiguity.

In 2009, we embarked on a research program into the way in which the French State reports on its performance through the mechanism of annual performance projects and annual performance reports, introduced by the organic law on finance laws (LOLF) and implemented as of the 2006 budget. It was this law that institutionalized public performance monitoring in legal terms. Our choice was motivated by the high level of ambition displayed by the law, its promoters and supporters, by the general character and

endogenous coercive isomorphism of the system introduced, which applies to all central government missions and is homogeneous, by the availability of information and the relatively pioneering methodological transparency, as well as by the possible comparison of results with foreign systems, in particular the American Government Performance Review Act (GPRA). Our analysis of the annual performance projects (PAPs) and annual performance reports (RAPs) appended to LOLF Finance Acts, based on large-scale sampling, has led us to draw up a typology of the discrepancies that can be observed between the stated aim of performance reporting for the benefit of parliamentarians and, beyond that, citizens, and the reality of what the State reports on in these documents (Gibert and Benzerafa-Alilat, 2016).

In the course of our work, we have been able to emphasize:

- Persistent discrepancies between objectives and indicators, confirming that the link between these two types of object remains the missing link in performance monitoring in the public sector¹
- The relative ease of locating the respective "topographical" positioning of the two objects (objective and indicator) and the relative ease of the ensuing quality audit
- The relative insensitivity of the nature of the indicators to political changes in state government, and the consequences of all these phenomena on the reality of the accountability practiced (*in use*) by the state, through its PAPs and RAPs, in relation to the accountability displayed (*espoused*).

This work was based on a cross-functional approach. Our ambition was to achieve a high level of validity, which led us to carry out a series of research studies based on sampling within the population of the State's general budget missions.

More recently, we have taken an interest in the rise of costing for accountability purposes (Benzerafa-Alilat and Gibert, 2021). Our work has revealed the persistence of cooptation between government departments pursuing, in a new context, a guerrilla war over competence that was already noticeable at the beginning of the 21st^{ème} century. Over time, it has shown that the contrast between the increasing abstraction of aggregate performance reporting and its de-intellectualization in the name of refocusing on the daily lives of citizens has become more pronounced. In order to complete our analysis of the State's accountability practices and give them more "flesh", we felt it would be useful to focus this new work on a specific field, so as to be able to situate the performance budget documents in relation to the various management tools, procedures and objects that interfere with them. To this end, we have chosen the case of the Agriculture and Food Mission of the General State Budget.

In Part I, we present the main features of the financial organization and management of this mission, before going on in Part II to discuss the concepts used in the performance component of the LOLF and how they differ from those traditionally used in management control or policy analysis. Part III is devoted to an analysis of the consequences of these discrepancies.

I. Case Study: The Agriculture and Food mission of the General State Budget

Since the introduction of the LOLF in 2006, the existence of a budget based primarily on the concept of public policy has led analysts to distinguish two different structures in a sector-based approach, even though they may overlap to a large extent: the organizational structure on the one hand, and the budgetary structure on the other. The organizational structure stems from the distribution of competences, missions - in the sense of attributions - and activities of the various government departments in the field taken as a case study. At the pinnacle of the structure are the ministries - freely made and unmade by the composition of governments and their reshuffles. At the start of 2022, this is the Ministry of Agriculture and Food. Within a ministry, the first-level elements are essentially the so-called central administration directorates, but also a general secretariat grouping together several support services (personnel, finance, public relations, etc.) and, in a complementary manner, various services or missions, not to mention the minister's cabinet. The latter is, in principle, the least perennial body, since its lifespan ends on the day the minister ceases to hold office. The directorates comprise sub-directorates, which in turn are made up of offices. While actual organizational structures and the vocabulary commonly used may vary somewhat, the traditional structure of French administration is based on the trilogy of directorates - sub-directorates - offices.

At level 1, the Ministry of Agriculture comprises the General Secretariat and 4 directorates:

- Corporate Economic and Environmental Performance Department
- French Food Directorate
- Education and Research Department
- Direction des pêches maritimes et de l'aquaculture.

The organizational structure is not limited to the central administration, but also includes the decentralized departments responsible for implementing the Ministry's policies and actions throughout the country. At regional level, these are the Directions Régionales de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la Forêt (DRAAF), which work under the direction of the regional prefect, but under the authority of the Minister of Agriculture (Decree no. 2004-374 of April 29, 2004), and at departmental level, the Directions Départementales de l'Emploi, du Travail, des Solidarités et de la Protection des Populations (DDETSPP)², interministerial departments with a wide range of responsibilities, which in turn report to the departmental prefect. Outside the Ministry itself, but under its supervision or the joint supervision of two or more ministries, there are a number of public bodies which also help to implement agricultural policies. These include ANSÉS - Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire, de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail, Office National des Forêts, and agricultural and veterinary colleges. Most of these bodies are public administrative establishments, public establishments of a professional, scientific or cultural nature, or more exceptionally, public establishments of an industrial and commercial nature, such as the Office National des Forêts.

The budgetary structure is based on the LOLF, which stipulates that Parliament votes the budget by mission, which are considered to be public policies, each grouping together a number of programs, which in turn are considered to be "public policy elements". Budgetary constraints are applied at program level, insofar as program managers are free to transfer funds within³ programs, but not between programs. The subdivision of programs into actions presented in the budget is indicative.

In 2022, the agriculture and food mission will comprise three programs: no. 149 "Competitiveness and sustainability of agriculture, agrifood, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture", no. 206 "Agriculture and food", and no. 208 "Agriculture, agrifood, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture".

"Food safety and quality" and no. 215 "Conduct and management of agricultural policies".

Two programs piloted and managed by the Ministry are outside the scope of the agriculture and food mission. The first is attached to the interministerial mission for research and higher education, n°142 "Agricultural higher education and research"; the second is attached to the interministerial mission for school education, n°143 "Agricultural technical education".

II. Unstable Concepts

Following instructions from the Budget Department, all program management controllers continue to use a trilogy of indicators⁴ which unambiguously combine a point of view and an indicator.

The citizen's point of view is associated with socio-economic efficiency: "The objectives of socio-economic efficiency state the expected benefit of the State's action for the citizen and the community in terms of modifying economic, social, environmental, cultural and health realities...". The user's benefit is associated with the quality of the service provided. That of taxpayers is associated with management efficiency, i.e., the expression of "expected productivity gains in the use of resources consumed, or the ratio of service activity to resources consumed".

Budgetary doctrine also requires that, as far as possible, a quantitative balance be achieved between the three types of indicator for each program⁵. In the PAP of the agriculture mission for 2022 (see table I), the figures are far from revealing this balance.

Table I: Breakdown of indicators by type according to agriculture and food programs

Viewpoint	PAP 215	PAP 149	PAP 206
User	2	1	
Citizen	1	9	3
Taxpayer	4	3	2
Total	7	13	5

Reasoning in terms of sub-indicators confirms the imbalance.

Table II: Breakdown of sub-indicators according to LOLF typology (side B)

	Efficiency		Service quality		Socio-economic efficiency		Total	
	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%
Prog 149	2	12%	1	6%	14	82%	17	100%
Prog 209	3	30%	0	0%	7	70%	10	100%
Prog 215	13	76%	3	18%	1	6%	17	100%
Total	18	41%	4	9%	22	50%	44	100%

Table II shows that the ideal of a balance for each program has hardly been achieved. Program 149 is overwhelmingly geared towards socio-economic effectiveness, as is 209 but to a lesser degree, and 215 towards efficiency. Service quality still seems to be lagging behind. The strong differentiation between the structure of indicators for programs 149 and 209, on the one hand, and 215, on the other, seems well-founded insofar as the latter are public policy programs that aim to preserve or bring about social change, whereas 215 is a support program whose major role is to provide resources, particularly human resources, to the other programs. This is consistent with the importance of economic efficiency for the first two programs, and its marginality for the third. On the other hand, the overall weakness of service quality indicators, which we can more or less associate with the level of achievements supposed to capture the relationship with the user, is surprising. The agriculture mission has its users: farmers, the agri-food industry, to whom it provides services through program 149 in particular, or imposes constraints through the program 215 in particular. The reason for this scarcity of service quality indicators is, a priori, obscure.

It would seem logical that, instead of seeking to emphasize a balance that seems designed to underline the fact that the State works for all and for everyone, and is concerned with the economy of public funds, the shares of the types of indicators should be justified by the type of goods produced by each program: final or so-called public policy program (private or public goods) on the one hand, and support program on the other. As the latter are responsible for managing resources, they have greater responsibility in terms of efficiency (although they do not bear sole responsibility for it). The endogenous coercive isomorphism whose perverse effects we have highlighted elsewhere is decidedly prevalent in Lolfian performance monitoring.

Management control emphasizes the difference between efficiency and effectiveness, which are confused in other disciplines such as economics, or by dictionaries. Efficiency relates a result obtained to the means or resources consumed to achieve that result. It is a representation of economists' classic production function, a more or less complete ratio of output to input. Completeness reaches its maximum when a full cost is used as an indicator of efficiency, and is low when production is related to a single factor of production - whereas a plurality of factors are consumed in the action of creative destruction (as in the case of partial productivity indicators such as labor productivity or yields per hectare). There are at least two main types of efficiency measurement: a priori (desired or forecast efficiency) and ex post (actual or observed efficiency).

Effectiveness is the ratio of a result obtained to a desired result (quantified objective or target value). It therefore relates reality to intention. There is therefore only one type of measurement⁶.

Ontologically, effectiveness and efficiency are not opposites. The idea of making them watertight categories stems from the telescoping between the classic management control distinction and the chain of public action, which was popularized in France at the time of the rationalization of budgetary choices (RCB). The public action chain is a generic representation of the process from the consumption of resources by a public authority or group of authorities to the impact of this process with regard to the final objective targeted by a public policy (Gibert 2022).

In its simplest form, this chain linearly includes four elements:

Resources → Activities → Achievements → Impact

As a result of the above generally accepted definitions, effectiveness and efficiency can be estimated or identified at several levels in any organization. Efficiency can relate to the company's entire value chain, or be calculated for a portion of it entrusted to a department, workshop, distribution network, etc. Efficiency can be calculated whenever a quantified ambition is put forward. Effectiveness can be calculated whenever a quantified ambition is put forward.

The typology adopted by the authors of the LOLF application texts has complicated their schema by allowing themselves to be influenced by a stakeholder logic. The aim is to be accountable to citizens, users and taxpayers in a relatively balanced way.

The association of socio-economic effects with the citizen suggests that these effects are a kind of collective good from which all citizens benefit. A position a priori close to that of Wildavsky when he stated that these goods are "in our heads", which seems to refer to the impact of a program as the realization of a collective good. However, this position poses a formidable problem, since the expression of the objective whose impact is described as a socio-economic effect is not necessarily appreciated by all citizens, and its usefulness felt by some may be matched by a disutility felt by others.

The category of users is also heterogeneous, insofar as it includes quasi-customers benefiting from a service they choose, obliged users benefiting from a service that is de facto compulsory for them (passports for travellers outside the European Union, driving licenses for prospective drivers), as well as people sanctioned by the State (motorists penalized by a parking ticket, inmates of the penitentiary system). It therefore ignores the precise mode of relationship with the State, which is fundamental if we wish to reason in terms of public value.

The category of taxpayer does not a priori raise similar problems of heterogeneity with regard to the value (private or collective good) created by the action of the State, but it does imply the idea that the possible reduction in tax pressure brought about by an improvement in efficiency is experienced positively by every taxpayer. This postulate is not obvious to those who do not pay income tax, due to the phenomenon of fiscal illusion,

in particular that created by the discreet nature of the first of all indirect taxes - VAT. All French people pay taxes, but many do not behave like taxpayers.

Overall, the Lolfian trilogy appears to be a construct whose foundation and usefulness are hard to see. All the more so since, if there is a recommendation as to the balance to be observed between the three types of indicators, this balance concerns the number of indicators of each type, and not the budgetary volumes that would be put under control by each. In other words, the distributive considerations that might be seen behind the triptych do not give rise to an answer to the question "who benefits from public action?" or to the question of the share of each of the three stakeholders in the results of public action. Irrespective, therefore, of the possibly questionable character of the qualifications of each indicator (cf. below), the trilogy seems unnecessary or intended to give an impression of abstract balance in the accountability mechanism.

The other side of the coin is more or less inspired by basic management control concepts. The association of socio-economic efficiency with the citizen suggests that this is considered in terms of impact. Matching service quality to the user suggests that this quality is assessed in terms of achievements, since it is these that the user consumes. On the other hand, matching efficiency to the taxpayer does not allow us to prejudge the level of appreciation of efficiency in the public action chain. Indeed, better productivity in an activity can relieve pressure on the taxpayer, as can a better ratio between the impact of a public policy and the achievements required to obtain it. We might therefore expect a fairly wide dispersion of efficiency indicators along the public action chain.

III. Is the quest for simpler, more aggregated accountability an illusion?

To study the problems of implementing the Lolfian trilogy on the example of the agricultural mission, we thought it appropriate to draw up a matrix with the different values of side B of the trilogy at the head of the columns, and the four generally accepted positions in the chain of public action at the head of the rows (plus an "indeterminate" row for the indicators that seemed to us to be "indeterminate").

Unclassifiable). We then positioned each of the 44 sub-indicators included in the PAPs of the three programs of the agriculture mission on the public action chain⁷.

		Qualification in PAP		
		Service quality	Efficiency	Socio-economic efficiency
	Resources		C 311, C 312, C 313, C 315, C 332, C 335	
Place in	Activity	A 311, C 111	B 321, B 322, C 314, C 334	A 421, A 431, B 211, B 212, B 311
the chain	Achievements	C 121	A 411, B 221, C 211, C 321, C 322	A 221, A 231, A 251
action			A 111	A 121, A 131, A 141, A 211, A 212, A 241,
public	Impact			B 111, B 112, B 113, B 121, C 221
	Unspecified	C 112	C 212, C 331	A 132, A 142, A 242

Table III shows the result of our reclassification. We have coded the sub-indicators ourselves. The letter indicates the program to which they belong: A for program 149, B for program 206, C for program 215. The first digit is the number of the objective, of the program, to which the objective indicator relates. The second digit is the number of the indicator within the objective to which it relates. These two figures are taken from the PAP or RAP in question. The third number situates the sub-indicator within the indicator it describes. For example, sub-indicator B 321 "time taken to process inspection reports" is the first sub-indicator of indicator n°2 of the third objective of the second program. The list of indicators and the questions raised by their classification are presented in Appendix 1.

The following table shows the structure of indicators for each program, according to our classification along the public action chain. The most striking feature is that if we combine activity and output indicators - as government departments often tend to do more or less deliberately - the rise of this pairing represents 51% of the mission's indicators, and the fact that impact accounts for only 35% of the indicators, compared with the 50% attributed by the PAP to socio-economic efficiency. Alternatively, if we consider that it is at the level of achievements and impacts that we can apprehend public performance, we will observe that 43% of indicators concern means or their arrangement, and therefore that performance accountability bites hard on the left-hand side of the public action chain. Optimists will take this to mean that PAPs and RAPs provide information that goes back to the causes, by going back to the means, and that in a document that is, after all, financial, this is only natural. Critics will observe that this is just one of many examples of the paradox caused by the sinister nature of indicators and the dextrism of objective formulation in public management.

Table IV: Breakdown of sub-indicators along the policy hate (by program)

	Resources		Activities		Achievements		Impact		Total	
	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%
Prog 149	0	0%	3	20%	4	27%	8	53%	15	100%
Prog 209	0	0%	5	50%	1	10%	4	40%	10	100%
Prog 215	6	40%	3	20%	4	27%	2	13%	15	100%
Total	6	15%	11	28%	9	23%	14	35%	40	85%

A detailed reading of the indicators (cf. appendix 1) suggests confirmation of the difficulties or errors in setting up indicators noted in the literature along the way:

The classification in the category of economic efficiency of phenomena whose attribution to public action is quite debatable and may seem to be *wishful thinking*. Such is the case with A131 "Evolution of French international market share for agricultural or agri-food products..." or even more so with A 132 "Evolution of the number of exporting companies", which appears to be purely statistical if we mean by this the measurement of the state of a phenomenon and not the evolution of a phenomenon attributable to public action. On the other hand, it is rare to find any attempt to take a statistical approach to the impact of this action, as is the case with A 212 "Gap between the rate of maintenance of subsidized facilities and the rate of maintenance of unsubsidized facilities".

This observation suggests that, despite the use of the term "evaluation" and certain related concepts, the performance section of the LOLF is a long way from an evaluative exercise.

The frequency of indicators of compliance with a rule adopted (or adopted by the administration). This is the case for B 311 "rate of completion of interministerial exercises to prepare for health crisis management", A 421 and A 431, B2111 and B212, all five of which are described as socio-economic efficiency indicators (SEE), even though they bring the activities of the programs concerned under control. Closer to internal control than to management control, and implying a strong prevalence of procedural rationality in the administration, these indicators can only be qualified as SEE if we assume that compliance with these standards is, more or less directly, a factor of SEE. In this way, what is supposed to be a measure of ESR could include practically all its possible causes. In this way, the effect can be traced back to a cause that can be considered both hypothetical and marginal.

A number of A 221, A 231 and A 251 indicators monitor shares or structures of production or types of clientele within a program action. They may be interesting in one way or another, but they can only be qualified as ESR indicators by a very broad extension of this concept.

All three of the above observations point to a more or less deliberate over-qualification of PAP and RAP indicators as SEEs. The fact that, for all the missions of the general budget, 55% of the indicators are for the citizen, 30% for the taxpayer and 16

% only for the user (Ministère de l'économie, des finances et de la relance, 2021) gives way to the hypothesis that the choice of qualifications is oriented towards the noblest category, and that in the face of rising public consumerism and the more or less significant capture of ministries by their publics, the semantics used by the way the LOLF is implemented aims to contribute to the myths of the pursuit of the general interest and the provision of the public good.

The same conclusion can be drawn from the very broad interpretation of the notion of efficiency. This is revealed by the construction of indicator A 111, which is out of phase with the phenomenon that the program manager wishes to bring under control; the inclusion (A 411) in the efficiency category of an indicator of the deployment of an organization's mission; the inclusion of an indicator of deadlines - without any reference to resources...

However, the performance guide expressly mentions among the indicators to be eliminated⁸ *"activity or production indicators that reflect the activity of agents or the material production of a service and measure the result of the service's production process"*, which *"do not reflect a true measure of performance"* (Actions et comptes publics, 2019, p. 24).

Aggregate or choose, or the dilemma of the search for more expressive accountability.

Parliamentarians have long complained about the excessive number of indicators included in PAPs and RAPs, and to a large extent have succeeded in reducing them⁹, from 1,297 in 2007 to 765 in 2018. This move was completed by the inclusion of a new category of indicators, initially absent from the Lolfian documents, in the introductory section of the PAPs devoted to a mission before the PAPs for each program.

"Mission-level indicators, emblematic of the ministry's policies and committed priorities, must be directly related to the political priorities carried by the mission" (Ministry of Public Action and Accounts, 2019, p. 21)

For the agriculture mission and for 2022, the combination of these indicators gives the following innominate dashboard (rearranged by the authors).

Table V: Mission (or main mission) indicators for the agriculture mission.

Program	Objective	Indicator	Sub-indicator	Code
P149	Combining the economic and environmental performance of farms, food processing and forestry (P149)	Public aid to agriculture / Gross operating surplus of agricultural enterprises		A 111
			Share of cultivated area in organic farming as a percentage of utilized agricultural area (U.A.A.)	A 121
P206	Promote changes in practices to protect public health and the environment (P206)	Controlling the use of pesticides and antibiotics	Number of pesticide unit doses sold (Ecophyto plan)	B 211
			Cumulative number of uses for all marketing authorizations (MA) products containing glyphosate	B 212
			Level of treatment of animals with colistin (Ecoantibio plan) ALEA colistin X100	B 213

It should be noted that the two objectives selected concern the two public policy programs (149 and 206), the support program (215) being absent, and that the authors of the PAP had classified 5 of the 6 sub-indicators selected as SEE. The co-authors of this communication have placed all 6 at impact level. The hypothesis that the choice of the most representative indicators reinforces the emphasis placed on the right-hand side of the public action chain should be tested in a more transversal study.

It should also be noted that no mission-specific or ad hoc indicators have been developed. "An ad hoc indicator is a synthetic indicator that does not come from one of the mission's programs. For example, the PISA indicator for student achievement at age 15 can be considered synthetic for all programs in the School Education mission" (Ministère action et compte publics, 2019).

This is all the more disturbing given the impression one gets from reading programs 149 and 206 that the former was more focused on agricultural activities per se, and was the driving force behind them, while the latter was more focused on environmental concerns and health control, and was more of a brake on agricultural and food activity. One has the feeling that the very understandable tension between these two major orientations, partly resolved in management terms by the separation of aims between the two programs and the differentiation of the 2 Ministry departments in charge of them, is the subject of rhetorical treatment at the level of the expression of objectives, but cannot be tackled at the level of indicators that would put the compromises under control, or balance to

We need to strike a balance between agricultural production, financial equilibrium and health and environmental concerns (not to mention food self-sufficiency, an issue brought back to the fore by current international events). In addition to the intellectual and cognitive difficulties involved in setting up indicators, we can put forward as an obstacle to their development the inappropriateness, from a political point of view, of reasoning in terms of tensions, rather than continuing to respond to antinomies in public management by segmenting fields and monitoring them.

The quest for a more aggregated account of performance has also resulted in the Budget Department producing a document entitled "Public Performance Data". In the words of the Budget Director, this document offers "a synthetic and graphic view of the results obtained by twenty-five missions of the State's general budget in terms of public expenditure performance." (Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Recovery, 2021). In fact, for each mission and each of its programs, the number of sub-indicators falling into the following result categories is counted: target achieved (target value or revision for the year in question), target not achieved but improvement on the previous year, no improvement and target not achieved and data not provided.

Table VI below compares the distribution obtained for the agriculture mission and its 3 programs with the result for all 25 missions of the general budget.

	Year	Target reached	Improvement	No improvement	No data information
All missions	2020	49%	6%	28%	16%
Mission: Agriculture, food, forestry and rural affairs	2018	57%	27%	9%	7%
	2019	58%	8%	23%	10%
	2020	60%	11%	19%	11%
Prog 149	2019	67%	0%	6%	28%
	2020	50%	17%	22%	11%
Prog 215	2019	50%	10%	40%	0%
	2020	72%	0%	11%	17%
Prog 206	2019	60%	20%	20%	0%
	2020	55%	18%	27%	0%

Source: authors, based on data from the document *Public Performance 2021*.

The ordinal ranking of the first three columns (the fourth column reveals a gap in the statistical chain, but cannot be considered the worst situation) does not allow for an overall rating per line, and only permits a ranking in fortunate conjunctions. This is the case for the comparison of the situation of the agriculture mission with that of all missions in 2020. The latter appears superior to the former from all points of view.

However, this combination can be exceptional and, above all, counting by category doesn't mean much. A target is all the more easily reached if its level has been set prudently; an improvement can be minimal, achieved in comparison with a catastrophic previous year, or on the contrary be highly commendable and still not have enabled the target to be reached, simply because of excessive ambition. In other words, results can only be assessed (among other things) in relation to the level of ambition. While analysis of the PAPs in detail gives some idea of the causes of deviations, the public performance document by its very nature conceals this information and thus presents insignificant figures. The meaningless palliative that is performance of performance. This type of quantification does not seem to contribute anything to any of the eight possible purposes of quantification listed by Behn (2003, p. 588) evaluate, control, budget, motivate, promote, celebrate, learn, improve. These are the reasons for the multiplicity of indicators, since a single measurement system cannot meet all these motivations.

After the mission indicators and performance data, the third document - the result of a desire to go beyond the LOLF's somewhat broken-mirror approach to monitoring - is the barometer of public action results. It is published and updated by the Interministerial Directorate for Public Transformation (DITP). Its aim is to monitor the commitments made by the President of the Republic and his government, with an emphasis on the concrete through the use of everyday objects, and it seems to be a vehicle for criticism of the abstract nature of some of the LOLF objectives, of their overly timeless character, not sufficiently impregnated with the orientations or commitments of today's leaders. For this reason, the barometer only monitors areas or elements of interest to the population (Benzerafa-Alilat and Gibert, 2021).

In this barometer, within the "theme" of agriculture, we find two priority policies. The first is aimed at "Reducing the use of phytosanitary products and accelerating the ecological transition". Its indicators are "the percentage of land under organic farming" and "the number of farmers engaged in a certified agro-ecological transition process". We note that while the former, taken over from the PAP agriculture and considered in the latter as a mission indicator, can be seen as an impact or socio-economic efficiency indicator, the latter could be seen as a development indicator of procedural rationality, located upstream on the public action chain. As such, to consider it as an everyday object would be somewhat questionable, except for farmers.

The second aims to "Secure the payment of Common Agricultural Policy subsidies". Its indicator is the rate of beneficiaries paid on time. While the objective of the first policy appears to be fairly long-term, that of the second is circumstantial¹⁰; one is oriented towards the citizen-user, the other towards the corporation. As with many of the barometer's other themes, we have the feeling that the ministries have been asked to

contribute to an obligation with policies or measures that can obey the obligation of transparency and the possibility of releasing indicator values at departmental level¹¹ .

CONCLUSION

In comparison with our previous work on the performance aspect of LOLF finance laws, our examination of the case of the agriculture mission has enabled us to refine our assessment of the balances and imbalances that result from the organized quantification of a public policy area in accordance with LOLF application rules, and the attempts made to present more aggregated or simpler visions of public performance. Ultimately, three types of factors intermingle to explain the inadequacies and incongruities that readers - even those who are far removed from anti-managerialism or the denunciation of "government by the numbers" - feel when reading the accountability statements produced around the theme of "what is public money used for?". These three sets of factors relate respectively to technical problems, demonstrative will and level of ambition.

On the technical front, considerable progress has been made since the first budgets were produced in LOLF mode. Quasi-indicator sheets are now included in the PAPs, enabling the reader to In this way, it is possible to better understand the reason for the indicator, the reality of the phenomenon being monitored and, consequently, the relevance, degree of reduction and possible drawbacks of the sub-indicator with regard to the objective to which it is associated. There remains the problem of ad hoc mission indicators, which departments seem to have great difficulty in developing. It's true that the nature of the mission in budgetary law - a simple grouping of programs - is not conducive to significant work in this area. There is also the problem of qualifying indicators, but we can assume that this is not just a technical problem.

At the level of advocacy. The exercise of presenting a quantified performance for accountability purposes is by its very nature a hybrid one: it involves a process of objectivization, associated with the transition from discourse to figures, as well as a process of justification to the people or bodies to whom one is reporting. In the PAPs and RAPs, this work of justification is carried out not only by means of lengthy qualitative explanations-which are, moreover, largely standardized by the LOLF application texts-that surround the presentation of indicators, but also by hazardous pairings between objectives and sub-indicators, as well as by a qualification of indicators manifestly biased in favor of socio-economic efficiency. The disappearance of the interministerial program audit committee (Comité interministériel d'audit des programmes - CIAP), an ad hoc audit body set up in the early years of the LOLF, highlights the profoundly political nature of the problem, and the fact that it is up to the primary recipient of documents - parliament - to be more demanding and vigilant.

In terms of ambition, the inconclusive nature of the development of ad-hoc mission indicators, the public performance document and the public action barometer highlights the paradoxical obligation in which innovators are trapped. We're looking for an accountability tool that's light (small number of indicators), expressive (understandable by the greatest number) and properly representative of public performance. In other

words, we'd like a tool that transcends the complexity and contradictions of public action - inherent in the conjunction of the State's general competence and the extreme diversity of citizens' claims, *concerns and interests*. All this is based on objectives that are, for the most part, social constructs, and therefore debatable ad nutum. The obstacle to this quest for the grail is therefore ontological.

Foot Notes:

- 1) But not only, cf. the similar problem when implementing the Balanced Scorecard in companies.
- 2) Directions départementales de la protection des populations (DDPP) in the largest départements.
- 3) i.e. from one title to another (with the exception of personnel credits, which cannot receive credits from other titles).
- 4) Initially, in the LOLF doctrine, it was the objectives that were supposed to belong to a category; for years, this belonging has been attributed to the indicators. This is a curious fact, to say the least, since in the practice of PAPs and RAPs, many of the objects baptized indicators are never more than tables bringing together several measuring instruments called "sub-indicators", which are in fact the real indicators of the phenomena under control in the monitoring of budgetary performance. Within the same indicator, "sub-indicators" may belong to different groups, without this difference being indicated.
- 5) (<https://www.budget.gouv.fr/reperes/performance/articles/trois-types-dobjectifs-pour-apprecier-lefficacite-de-laction-public>)
- 6) Even if we can refine this, for example by doubling an efficiency calculated by a ratio between results and initial target values by an efficiency calculated by a ratio between results and corrected target values.
- 7) This determination is obviously based on expert opinion and has its limitations. It should be noted, however, that the first classification by the two co-authors resulted in 38 identical classifications, and that discussion of the six remaining cases led to agreement on the other six in the first round. All the discrepancies were due to a problem in understanding the explanations provided by the PAPs on the nature of each indicator.
- 8) To reduce the excessive number of these
- 9) At least the indicators labelled as such, since others are scattered throughout the textual sections of the PAPs and RAPs (Cf. Gibert and Benzerafa-Alilat, 2012).
- 10) "After significant delays in CAP aid payments from 2014 to 2017, the State has managed to re-establish a normal aid payment schedule since 2018 and to consolidate it since then. This measure tracks the restoration of the payment schedule since that date."
- 11) Given that one of the barometer's key ideas is to enable readers to compare the situation in their own département with national figures

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	Name	Explanation-notation
A 111	Public aid to agriculture / Gross operating surplus of agricultural enterprises	The aim is to maintain farms, not to minimize state support, otherwise we'd have to change the sub-indicator. This explains our impact classification
A121	Share of cultivated area in utilized agricultural area (U.A.A.)	No comment
A 131	Trends in France's international market share for agricultural and agri-food products, forestry-wood, bio-sources and the agricultural machinery	Impact, except that it looks more like a statistic, as the link with government actions is not obvious.
A132	Number of companies exporters	Idem in more marked, it is a pure statistic
A 141	Wood harvest to production ratio biological	Sustainable development efficiency
A 142	Sawn timber volume	This is a pure statistic. The gist of indicators are dedicated to the previous sub-indicator

A 211	Weight of assisted installations	The indicator relates the number of facilities assisted to the total number of business start-ups under 40.
A 212	Gap between "retention rate assisted installations" and "rate of retention of non-assisted farms".	An attempt, quite rare in pap and Rap, to identify a typical impact using a differential.
A 221	Share of ICHN beneficiaries in the total of CAP aid applicants	What does the citizen have to do with it? a breakdown of achievements
A 231	PCAE beneficiaries as a proportion of all CAP aid applicants	Ditto, but more pronounced, it's a statistic.
A 241	Percentage of forest area managed by local authorities	Let's assume that development is the ultimate goal
A 242	Number of additional hectares of private forest under an approved sustainable management document (DGD)	We can assume that the number of documents is an achievement and that the surface area covered is an impact.
A 251	Rate of cut wood in state-owned forests	Repartition de réalisation + meilleure mise en valeur des state forests (on this second point it would be the taxpayer
A 311	Number of dossiers (1st pillar, ICHN, MAEC-BIO) paid on time	
A 411	Ratio of the number of at-sea inspections led by the Centre National de Surveillance des Pêches (CNSP) to the total number of inspections. declared in the SATI database	achievements for the national center in question
A 421	Number of inspections of fishing vessels at sea and on landing as a proportion of the number of inspections at sea and on landing. landing plan	Programming compliance indicator
A 431	Inspections carried out in response to needs identified in inter-regional and regional control plans (PIRC/PRC)	Programming compliance indicator
B 111	Number of pesticide unit doses sold (Ecophyto plan)	The ultimate aim seems to be to curb sales
B 112	Cumulative number of uses for all marketing authorizations (MAs) for products containing glyphosate	idem
B 113	Level of treatment of animals with colistin (Ecoantibio plan) ALEA colistin X 100	idem
B 121	Geographical coverage of territorial food projects	It's hard to believe that making paper is an efficiency for the citizen, but it's an impact because the State doesn't design territorial projects.
B 211	Rate of marketing authorization dossiers processed by ANSES within deadlines regulations	Very extensive concept of for the citizen: it makes them go home and do their job properly
B 212	Rate of urgent referrals handled on time contractual	Idem

B 221	Rate of non-compliant inspections resulting in administrative or criminal proceedings	This time they're passing it on to the taxpayer, no doubt because it's a way of bringing in money.
B 311	Rate of completion of interministerial emergency preparedness exercises health crisis	Programming compliance indicator
B 321	Processing time for inspection reports	It's more a question of service quality than efficiency. Visit resources consumed are not explained
B 322	Rate of samples analyzed exploitable	This can be interpreted as the productivity of levies
C 111	% of files processed by teleprocedure	
C 112	Total number of people who used a tele-procedure	The assumption is made that the objective is to increase the number of people having used a tele-procedure
C 121	Survey dematerialization rate regular statistics: Farming and forestry	The aim is to generalize dematerialization
C 211	Manager/managed ratio	A kind of managerial productivity
C 212	Managed headcount	Statistics
C 221	Percentage of employees benefiting from the employment obligation set out in law no. 87-517 of July 10, 1987	The objective itself is a good example of the confusion between the search for work efficiency and the application of a policy. for disabled workers.
C 311	SUN/workstation ratio	This ratio and the 2 following ones are examples of efficiency inducers who only relate means. And not outputs on means (SUN = net floor area)
C312	Routine maintenance / SUB ratio	See above (SUB gross floor area)
C 313	Heavy maintenance / SUB ratio	Ditto
C314	Aggregate calendar deviation rate for projects infrastructure	Weighted average of the difference between the discounted and actual durations initially planned.
C 315	Aggregate budget deviation rate for infrastructure projects	Weighted average of variances between updated and original budgets.
C 321	Gains on purchasing operations	Based "on a comparison between: - reference prices or "situations"; - new prices or a new situation The price or cost differential is multiplied by the annual volume". Can be considered as a realization of a support service.
C 322	Purchasing performance rate	Idem 321 but in relative value
C 331	Office efficiency ratio	Mysterious. Methodology not explained
C 332	Number of office workstations	simple enumeration
C 333	Aggregate calendar deviation rate for IT projects	"weighted average of the differences between updated and Indicator of adherence to schedule
C 334	Aggregate project budget variance rate IT	"Weighted average of variances between updated budgets and initially planned budgets".